

DESIGN OF FIBER PREFORMS FOR WORLD'S LARGEST FIBERGLASS COMPANY

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ABSTRACT

Fiberglass preforms or fabrics are a main structural form for making glass fiber reinforced plastics (FRPs). Once the properties of fiber and matrix and fiber volume fraction are fixed, the mechanical properties of the FRP products are predominantly dependent on the structural parameters of the fabrics, i.e., fiber arrangement angles and areal weights. It is a difficult task to experimentally determine those parameters. Not only does high expenditure both in time and in money have to be spent, but also it is hardly possible to obtain an optimized design only through the trial-and-error tests. This paper describes how to design the two structural parameters of any multiaxial fabric only based on the mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix materials. The load shared by any layer of the FRP is determined through the classical laminate theory, whereas the homogenized stresses in the fiber and matrix of this layer are calculated using micromechanics Bridging Model. The homogenized quantities are then converted into true stresses before compared with the fiber and matrix strength data to assess whether or not the layer is failed. If there is a fiber failure, or there is a matrix failure together with a maximum strain of the laminate which is greater than a critical value, the corresponding load applied on the FRP is defined as its ultimate strength. All of the design formulae involved are explicit and analytical, and the designed performances of the resulting FRPs agree well with the experimental counterparts. The present work provides an efficient methodology for engineering applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to high stiffness and strength to weight ratios, excellent anti-fatigue and anti-corrosion properties, low fabrication cost, and easy to mold in one-step, fiberglass reinforced plastics (FRPs) have become the best candidate material for emerging industries such as large wind turbine blades, nacelle covers, yachts, pipelines, and have shown attractive application prospects in lightweight vehicles and rail transit. The large demand for these industries has given birth to the rapid development of China's fiberglass manufacturing industry. In 2017, China's annual output of fiberglass has accounted for more than 60% of the world's total output. Among them, China Jushi Co., Ltd's annual output of glass fiber reached 1.5 million tons, exceeding 22% of the world's total output.

Fiberglass is the main load-bearing body of FRP. As a reinforcing material, composite with resin matrix mainly adopts two structural forms. The first one is fiberglass reinforced plastics (FRP) products made from single filament (fiber bundle) by filament winding, including automatic laying and tape laying, which are developed in recent years. The latter realizes a certain width of filament winding side by side. Traditional filament winding production efficiency is relatively low, products generally need a rotating shaft, and often need to dip the filament beams before winding. During winding process, harmful gases will be released (automatic wire laying and automatic tape laying mostly use semi-intervention impregnating material, which reduces the release of harmful gases). At present, in many places, due to environmental protection is not up to the standard. Another dominant structural form is to pre-fabricate fiber fabrics, including warp and weft knitted fabrics, according to the design requirements. Users only need to cut the fiber fabrics and lay them in different moulds. With the help of RTM, RIM or hand lay-up process, fiber fabrics with different shapes and properties are prepared by dipping and curing with resin. If the fiber tows contain resin, such as the prefabricated fiber fabric after blending thermoplastic matrix fibers with reinforced glass fibers, users will use hot pressing process to form, which will greatly shorten the forming cycle.

Obviously, the mechanical properties of FRP products depend on the orientation angle of fiber tows and the amount of fibers used in different orientations when the properties of fibers and matrix remain unchanged and the content of fibers is fixed. In the industry, the amount of fibers is measured by areal weight (g/m^2). For example, the triaxial fabric $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$, labeled as TLX1215 and provided by Zhejiang Hengshi Co., Ltd (a subsidiary of the China Jushi which makes fabrics preforms using the fiberglasses from the China Jushi), has a total areal weight of $1219\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, in which 0° fiberglasses are in a areal weight of $708\text{g}/\text{m}^2$ and $+45^\circ$ and -45° fiberglasses consume an equal areal weight of $250\text{g}/\text{m}^2$. The remaining $11\text{g}/\text{m}^2$ areal weight is assumed by PET, a polyester suture, to stitch all of the fiberglasses as a whole.

How to design the most suitable fiber bundle direction angle and areal weight according to different application requirements has become a technical problem that the fiber fabric production enterprises have to face, and also an important weight to measure the core competitiveness of enterprises. Although there are many methods for predicting the strength of laminates in the existing literature including textbooks [1-4], so far, the manufacturers of fiber fabric (such as Hengshi Co., Ltd) mainly rely on experience and proofing tests to determine the structural parameters of fiber fabric. The experimental workload is huge, which is not only time-consuming, but also difficult to achieve the optimal.

Based on the Bridging Model and matrix true stress theory, the stiffness and strength of FRP in any direction can be regarded as the explicit function of the orientation angle and weight of the fiber fabric only by inputting the original performance parameters of the fiber and matrix and the volume content of the fiber. By adjusting the fiber orientation angle and/or areal weight, the properties of the FRP can meet the application requirements, and the optimal design of the fiber fabric can be realized.

2 INTERNAL STRESS CALCULATION

In order to predict the properties of composites according to constituent properties and fiber geometry parameters, the stress field in fibers and matrix must be determined first.

As shown in Fig. 1, the fiber tows of each layer in the fiber fabric are arranged in parallel, and finally stitched into a whole by a small amount of polyester thread, which avoid the weakening of fiber bending at the interlacing position to the mechanical properties of the fibers and the production efficiency is higher compare with the alternating weft and warp woven fabric. A resin impregnated fabric is a typical laminate, and the stress analysis of each layer can be realized by the classical laminate theory.

Fig. 1. A multiaxial fiber fabric

It is assumed that the layers are symmetrical and the influence of the bending load is not considered in the performance design. Without loss of generality, the incremental scheme is adopted to solve the problem, the mid-surface strain increment of the laminate is determined by the following equation [5]:

$$h \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{xx}^0 \\ d\sigma_{yy}^0 \\ d\sigma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q'_{11} & Q'_{12} & Q'_{13} \\ Q'_{12} & Q'_{22} & Q'_{23} \\ Q'_{13} & Q'_{23} & Q'_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{xx}^0 \\ d\varepsilon_{yy}^0 \\ 2d\varepsilon_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{ij}^I = \sum_{k=1}^n (C_{ij}^G)_k t_k \quad (2)$$

$$h = \sum_{k=1}^n t_k \quad (3)$$

$$[(C_{ij}^G)_k] = ([T_{ij}]_c)_k ([S_{ij}]_k)^{-1} ([T_{ij}]_c^T)_k \quad (4)$$

n is the number of fiber layers and t_k is the thickness of the k^{th} layer. $[S_{ij}]_k$ is the compliance tensor of the k^{th} layer in its local coordinates and $[T_{ij}]_c$ is a coordinate transformation tensor [5].

Once the strains, $\{d\varepsilon_j^0\}^{(G)} = \{d\varepsilon_{11}^0, d\varepsilon_{22}^0, 2d\varepsilon_{12}^0\}^T$, are solved from Eq. (1), the internal stress increments in fiber and matrix of the k^{th} layer are found from^[1]

$$\{d\sigma_i^f\}_k = (V_f[I] + V_m[A_{ij}]_k)^{-1} \{d\sigma_j\}_k \quad (5)$$

$$\{d\sigma_i^m\}_k = [A_{ij}]_k (V_f[I] + V_m[A_{ij}]_k)^{-1} \{d\sigma_j\}_k, \{d\sigma_i\}_k = ([T_{ij}]_s)_k [(C_{ij}^G)_k] \{d\varepsilon_j^0\}^{(G)} \quad (6)$$

V_f is the fiber volume fraction, $[T_{ij}]_s$ is another coordinate transformation tensor, and $[A_{ij}]$ is defined by Bridging Model. Explicit formulas for A_{ij} are given in Appendix A. Further, the local compliance $[S_{ij}]_k$ is

$$[S_{ij}]_k = (V_f[S_{ij}^f]_k + V_m[S_{ij}^m]_k [A_{ij}]_k) (V_f[I] + V_m[A_{ij}]_k)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

$[S_{ij}^f]$ and $[S_{ij}^m]$ are the compliance tensors of the fiber and matrix, respectively.

3 MATRIX TRUE STRESS THEORY

It is noted that the stresses defined by Eqs. (1, 2) are homogenized quantities. They are based on the homogenization equation of composites:

$$d\sigma_i = \left(\int_{V'} d\tilde{\sigma}_i dV \right) / V' = V_f d\sigma_i^f + V_m d\sigma_i^m \quad (8)$$

It must be pointed out that the average error of composite ultimate strength obtained by homogenized stress can reach more than five times of the average error obtained by true stress [5]. This means that any performance calculation of the composite must be based on true stresses. In fact, the elastic performance calculation must also be based on the true stress, because the elastic constants of materials are independent of the stresses (as long as they are within the elastic limit range), and the elastic constants calculated by true stresses and homogenized stresses are equal, which conceals the fact that the elastic properties are also derived from true stresses. The stress field in the fiber is uniform [6,7], and its true stresses are the same as the homogenized stresses; the true stresses of the matrix are equal to the homogenized stresses multiplied by certain coefficients. The author still calls the coefficients the stress concentration factors of matrix. This is because the stress concentration occurs at the edge of the hole, when the hole is filled with heterogeneous fibers, stress concentration also occurs in the matrix.

However, the stress concentration factors of matrix are essentially different from that in the traditional sense. First, the traditional stress concentration is caused by geometric discontinuity in the structure (such as cracks, holes, sharp corner), but the stress concentration in composite is caused by material discontinuity between fiber and matrix. Secondly, the definition of the stress concentration factor of matrix is completely different from the traditional method. The traditional stress concentration factor is defined as: the maximum point stress in the material is divided by the applied stress, once the interface between fiber and matrix cracks, it will inevitably lead to infinite stress concentration factor in matrix, because the matrix stress at the interface crack tip is singular. To avoid singularity, the stress concentration factor of matrix is the average stress along a line divided by the homogenized stress.

Under a single transverse tensile load, the stress concentration factor of the matrix is [10]

$$K_{22}(\varphi) = \frac{1}{|\bar{R}_\varphi^b - \bar{R}_\varphi^a|} \int_{|\bar{R}_\varphi^a|}^{|\bar{R}_\varphi^b|} \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m}{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} d|\bar{R}_\varphi| \quad (9)$$

Where $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m$ is the stress in the matrix along the load direction (point stress) obtained by the concentric cylinder (infinitely long cylindrical fiber clamped in an infinite matrix), $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}$ is given by the Bridging Model (average stress of body), φ is the angle between the normal direction of the failure surface and the external load under given load, and \vec{R}_φ^a and \vec{R}_φ^b are the vectors of the fiber and the cylinder surface of matrix in the RVE, $b = a / \sqrt{V_f}$.

The stress fields of the matrix under different loads (calculated by the concentric cylinder model) are different, the failure surfaces are different, and the corresponding matrix stress concentration factors are also different. The derivation process of the matrix stress concentration factors under transverse interface, transverse compression, transverse shear and axial shear with the perfect interface is shown in [8,9,10,11]. For convenience, the explicit expressions of the transverse tensile, transverse compression and axial shear stress concentration factors of the matrix are given in Appendix B. The transverse tensile stress concentration factors of the matrix after interface cracking and the condition of interface cracking under arbitrary load are given in Appendix C.

It should be pointed out that the stress field of the matrix under axial tensile and compressive loads is uniform, so there is no stress concentration in the matrix under axial tension and compression. However, due to plastic deformation of resin or metal matrix materials, the actual stress shared by fibers under axial loading is higher than that shared by linear elastic matrix analysis. In order to compensate for the deviation of the axial stress caused by the linear elastic matrix and avoid the change of the failure mode, it is suggested in [5] that the axial stress correction factor is introduced after the fiber volume fraction reaches or exceeds 55%:

$$K_{11}^t = \min \left\{ 1, \frac{E_{11}^f \sigma_{u,t}^m}{E^m \sigma_{u,t}^f} \right\}, K_{11}^c = \min \left\{ 1, \frac{E_{11}^f \sigma_{u,c}^m}{E^m \sigma_{u,c}^f} \right\} \quad (10)$$

After obtaining the stress concentration factors of matrix, the true stresses of matrix are given by

$$\{\bar{\sigma}_i^m\}^{l+1} = \{\bar{\sigma}_i^m\}^l + \{K_{11} d\sigma_{11}^m, K_{22} d\sigma_{22}^m, K_{12} d\sigma_{12}^m\}^T, l=0, 1, \dots \quad (11)$$

$$K_{11} = \begin{cases} K_{11}^t, & \text{when } \sigma_{11}^m > 0 \\ K_{11}^c, & \text{when } \sigma_{11}^m < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$K_{22} = \begin{cases} K_{22}^t, & \text{when } d\sigma_{22}^m > 0 \text{ without interface crack} \\ \hat{K}_{22}^t, & \text{when } d\sigma_{22}^m > 0 \text{ with interface crack} \\ K_{22}^c, & \text{when } d\sigma_{22}^m < 0 \end{cases}$$

K_{22} and K_{12} are the stress concentration factors of the matrix in the composite corresponding to transverse and in-plane shear loads, respectively.

The true stress of fiber is the same as its homogenized stress:

$$\{\sigma_i^f\}^{l+1} = \{\sigma_i^f\}^l + \{d\sigma_i^f\}, l=0, 1, \dots \quad (12)$$

The load on the composite material is

$$\{\sigma_i\}^{l+1} = \{\sigma_i\}^l + \{d\sigma_{11}, d\sigma_{22}, d\sigma_{12}\}^T, l=0, 1, \dots \quad (13)$$

where l is the iteration step number, $\{d\sigma_i^m\} = \{d\sigma_{11}^m, d\sigma_{22}^m, d\sigma_{12}^m\}^T$ and $\{d\sigma_i^f\}$ are the homogenized stress increments of matrix and fiber calculated by (6.2) and (6.1). When the thermal residual stress is not taken into account, the initial values of $\{\bar{\sigma}_i^m\}^0$ and $\{\sigma_i^f\}^0$ are 0.

4 FAILURE CRITERIA

4.1 Interface crack criterion

The interface crack criterion under arbitrary load is that the Mises stress of the current true stress of

the matrix exceeds the critical value and the matrix must not be subjected to triaxial compression.

$$(\bar{\sigma}_e^m)^l \geq \hat{\sigma}_e^m \text{ and } (\bar{\sigma}_m^1)^l > 0 \quad (14)$$

Where $\hat{\sigma}_e^m = \sqrt{(\hat{\sigma}_{11}^m)^2 + (K_{22}^t \hat{\sigma}_{22}^m)^2 - K_{22}^t \hat{\sigma}_{11}^m \hat{\sigma}_{22}^m}$ and $(\bar{\sigma}_m^1)^l$ is the first principle stress of matrix.

4.2 Matrix failure criterion

A matrix failure is assessed through Tsai-Wu criterion (as isotropic materials are a subset of anisotropic composites):

$$F_1[(\bar{\sigma}_{11}^m)_l (\bar{\sigma}_{11}^m)_l + (\bar{\sigma}_{22}^m)_l (\bar{\sigma}_{22}^m)_l - (\bar{\sigma}_{11}^m)_l (\bar{\sigma}_{22}^m)_l] + F_2(\bar{\sigma}_{12}^m)_l (\bar{\sigma}_{12}^m)_l + F_3[(\bar{\sigma}_{11}^m)_l + (\bar{\sigma}_{22}^m)_l] \geq 1 \quad (15)$$

$$F_1 = 1/(\sigma_{u,t}^m \sigma_{u,c}^m), F_2 = 1/(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2, F_3 = 1/\sigma_{u,t}^m - 1/\sigma_{u,c}^m$$

Where $\sigma_{u,t}^m$, $\sigma_{u,c}^m$ and $\sigma_{u,s}^m$ are the tensile, compressive and shear strength of matrix.

4.3 Fiber failure criterion

A fiber failure is detected using maximum stress failure criteria against the fiber longitudinally tensile and compressive strengths:

$$(\sigma_f^1)^l \geq \sigma_{u,t}^f, \quad (\sigma_f^3)^l \leq -\sigma_{u,c}^f \quad (16)$$

Where $\sigma_{u,t}^f$ and $\sigma_{u,c}^f$ are longitudinal tensile and compressive strengths of the fiber, $(\sigma_f^1)^l$ and $(\sigma_f^3)^l$ are the first and third principal stresses of the fiber.

4.4 Fatal failure and non-fatal failure

Fiber failure is fatal failure, matrix failure is non-fatal failure. Once fatal failure occurs in any layer of the laminate, it is considered that the ultimate failure of the laminate is reached and the calculation should be terminated.

Stiffness degradation of failed layer is needed after non-fatal failure occurs. The stiffness degradation scheme is to reduce the modulus of the matrix to 1% of the original modulus.

$$E^m = 0.01E_0^m \quad (17)$$

Where E_0^m is the initial modulus of the matrix. Other material performance parameters, including the Poisson's ratio of the matrix, remain unchanged. The compliance matrix of matrix and bridging matrix are calculated based on the properties of fiber and matrix after degradation.

4.5 ultimate failure

An ultimate failure of the laminate is attained if either of the three conditions is fulfilled: (a) there is a fatal failure; (b) there is a matrix failure and a laminate strain in absolute value greater than the critical value, which is generally 5%, or selected according to experiment; (c) the matrix in all of the layer fails and stress of one layer fulfills normal Tsai-Wu criterion. The ultimate strength of the laminate is the external load corresponding to the ultimate failure.

5 ILLUSTRATION

5.1 Properties

The E7-UD1200 uniaxial fabric of Zhejiang Hengshi Co. Ltd. is mainly made of 0° fibers superimposed with a small amount of 90° fibers and stitched by polyester thread (see figure 2). Its structural parameters are listed in Table 1. It is made of epoxy RIMR035C resin of Hexion Company and laminated by RTM. The properties of the tested laminates are shown in Table 2. The properties of RIMR035C resin tested by Hansen are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 2. E-7 UD1200 uniaxial fiber fabric

0° Fiber			90° Fiber			Stitch Fiber	
Type	Diameter	Areal weight	Type	Diameter	Areal weight	Type	Areal weight
E-7	17μm	1152g/m ²	E-6	17μm	50g/m ²	PET	11g/m ²

Table 1: Structural parameters of E-7 UD1200 uniaxial fiber fabric

0° Tension		0° Compression		90° Tension		90° Compression		In-plane Shear	
E (GPa)	X (MPa)	E (GPa)	X' (MPa)	E (GPa)	Y (MPa)	E (GPa)	Y' (MPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	S (MPa)
46.3	1184.8	46.8	934.7	13.1	52	14.3	183.7	3.99	84.6

Table 2: Properties of E-7 UD1200/RIMR035C laminate ($V_f=53.9\%$)

E (GPa)	ν	$\sigma_{u,t}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{u,c}$ (MPa)
3.22	0.35	72.9	93.8

Table 3: properties of RIMR035C resin

The tensile and compressive modulus are approximately equal regardless of axial or transverse loading. Thus, the tensile and compressive modulus of the fiber and the matrix are considered to be the same, and elastic properties of matrix are given in Table 3.

The glass fiber is isotropic, so the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of fiber can be obtained from the data in Table 2. Because the axial performance test is usually more accurate than the transverse performance test, the fiber modulus 85GPa is obtained by the axial modulus. The Poisson's ratio of fiber is determined to be 0.29 with reference to the shear modulus and transverse modulus.

The matrix tensile strength of 72.9 MPa is credible because the transverse tensile strength of E-7 UD1200/RIMR035C predicted by it is 50.7 MPa, which is close to the measured value of 52 MPa. The tested matrix compressive strength of 93.8 MPa is not credible. the predicted transverse compressive strength of laminates based on 93.8 MPa is much lower than the test value 183.7 MPa; Therefore, the compressive strength should be calculated according to the transverse compressive strength of unidirectional plate. The compressive strength of matrix obtained from the formulas and Table 2 in this paper is 146 MPa. The matrix shear strength the is determined by the following Mohr formula

$$\sigma_{u,s}^m = 0.5 \sqrt{\sigma_{u,c}^m \sigma_{u,t}^m} = 51.6 \text{MPa} \quad (18)$$

It is assumed that the axial tensile and compressive failure are caused by fiber failure, and the axial tensile and compressive strengths of the fibers are respectively determined according to the axial tensile and compressive strength of unidirectional laminate. The properties of fibers and matrix are listed in Table 4.

	E_{11} (GPa)	ν_{12}	$\sigma_{u,t}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{u,c}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{u,s}$ (MPa)
Fiber	85	0.29	2150	1700	-
Matrix	3.22	0.35	72.9	146	51.6

Table 4: Mechanical properties of E-7 glass fiber and RIMR035C epoxy matrix

According to the data in Table 4 and the transverse tensile strength $Y=52\text{MPa}$, the transverse tensile stress concentration factor $K=6.18$ after interface cracking and the critical transverse tensile stress $\hat{\sigma}_{22}^0=54.7\text{MPa}>Y$ at cracking are obtained. It shows that the fiber-matrix interface of the material keeps perfect bonding until failure, and there will be no interface cracking. Therefore, it is only necessary to consider the stress concentration factors of matrix for the perfect interface under different fiber volume fraction.

5.2 Design of uniaxial fabric

The fiber of E7-UD1560 uniaxial fabric consist of 0° fibers with areal weight of 1512g/m^2 , 90° fibers with areal weight of 40g/m^2 and PET yarn with areal weight of 11g/m^2 . The fiber volume fraction of the laminate made from E7-UD1560 uniaxial fabric and RIMR035C is $V_f=58.3\%$.

Since the areal weight of 90° fibers is only 2.6% of the areal weight of 0° fibers, the laminate is considered to be a unidirectional composite. According to the data of Table 4, the elastic constants of the laminates calculated by Bridging Model are listed in Table 5. The data test by Hengshi Co., Ltd are also listed in Table 5. The difference of transverse modulus is obviously related to discreteness. The transverse compression modulus is 17 GPa. If the average values of transverse tensile and transverse compressive modulus are regarded as transverse modulus, the relative error is only 2.5%. The difference of shear modulus may be related to the test method. It is generally believed that the shear properties obtained by Iosipescu or 45° Rail shear test method are more credible, especially for the shear strength.

	$E_{11}(\text{GPa})$	$E_{22}(\text{GPa})$	ν_{12}	$G_{12}(\text{GPa})$	$G_{23}(\text{GPa})$
Experiment	52	14.3*	-	4.1**	-
Prediction	50.9	16.1	0.315	5.5	5.5
Error	-2.1%	12.6%	-	34.1%	-

* tensile modulus

** calculate according to $[\pm 45]_2$ laminates tensile modulus

Table 5. Elastic properties of E-7 UD1560 laminate

The stress concentration factors of matrix in E-7 glass fiber/RIMR035C with different fiber volume fraction are listed in Table 6. The uniaxial strengths of the laminate are listed in Table 7. The average error between theoretical prediction and experimental comparison is 7.8%. It is well known that the experimental data of composite materials, especially the strength test data, are generally discrete. In this paper, the strengths of composites are predicted based on the properties of fiber and matrix. Considering that there are many influence factors (cumulative error of constituent properties, discreteness of laminate test data, etc.), the accuracy of the prediction is adequate.

In order to illustrate the decisive role of the true stress of matrix on the failure and strength prediction of composite materials, the uniaxial strengths predicted based on the homogenized stress ($K_{11}^t=K_{22}^t=K_{22}^c=K_{12}=1$) are also listed in Table 7, with an average error of 101.2%, which is nearly 13 times higher than the prediction based on true stress error of 7.8%.

V_f	K_{11}^t	K_{11}^c	K_{12}	K_{22}^t	K_{22}^c
58.3%	0.895	1	1.47	3.26	2.05
53.7%	0.895	1	1.42	3.11	1.93

Table 6. Stress concentration factors of the matrix in E-7 glass fiber/RIMR035C composite

	X(MPa)	X'(MPa)	Y(MPa)	Y'(MPa)	S₁₂(MPa)
Experiment	1370	914	46.4	169	-
Prediction(with SCF)	1287.8	1018	49.2	181.4	77.4
Error	-6%	11.4%	6%	7.3%	-
Prediction(Homogenized stress)	1287.8	1018	155.4	426.5*	114
Error	-6%	11.4%	234.9%	152.3%	

* reach max strain

Table 7. Uniaxial strengths of E-7 UD1560 laminate

5.3 Design of multiaxial fabric

The fiber of E-7 TLX1215 triaxial fabric consist of 0° fibers with areal weight of 708g/m², ±45° fibers with areal weight of 250g/m² and PET yarn with areal weight of 11g/ m². The fiber volume fraction of the laminate made from E-7 TLX1215 triaxial fabric and RIMR035C is $V_f=53.7\%$.

The stress concentration factors calculated by constituent properties (Table 4) and fiber volume fraction are listed in Table 6.

The areal weight of the fibers of different angles is reflected by the thickness in laminate. The thickness of the +45° and -45° layers is taken as 1, and the thickness of the 0° layer is 2.832 (= 708 / 250).

According to the known parameters (constituent properties in Table 4, stress concentration factor in Table 6, ply angle and ply thickness) are substituted into the formulas in Sections 2 and 4. The modulus and strength of the triaxial fabric are calculated and listed in Table 8.

The results show that the average error of the elastic modulus prediction is 7.3%, and the average error of the ultimate strength prediction based on the matrix true stress theory is 10.4%. This result is satisfactory considering that the calculation is based entirely on fiber and matrix properties.

In order to compare the influence of stress concentration factors, the prediction base on homogenized stress is also the average error of prediction based on homogenized stress is 40.3%, which is nearly 4 times the error of prediction base on the true stress error at 10.4%. It should be noted that in this problem, most of the fibers are arranged in the 0° direction, and therefore, the strength predicted by the mean stress along 0° is sufficiently accurate because the matrix stress concentration along the fiber axis does not exist.

Overall, the stress concentration factors of matrix play a decisive role in failure strength prediction of composite.

	0 °Tension		0 °Compression		90 °Tension		90 °Compression	
	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
Experiment	33.6	800	35.5	660	14.3	126	14.7	207
Prediction (True Stress)	34.3	712.7	34.2	574.2	16.4	114.8	16.4	225.5
Error	1.8%	-11.4%	-3.7%	-13.2%	14%	-8.9%	10.9%	8.9%
Prediction (Homogenized Stress)		783.7		682		184.6		432.8
		-2%		3.3%		46.5%		109%
	In-plane Shear							
	Modulus	Strength						

	(GPa)	(MPa)
Experiment	7.94	216
Prediction (True Stress)	8.45	194.8
Error	6%	-9.8%
Prediction (Homogenized Stress)		304.1
		40.7%

Table 8. Moduli and strengths of E-7 TLX1215 $[0^0/\pm 45^0]_s$ laminate

Obviously, as long as the design requirements are given, the optimal ply angle and areal weight of fiber fabric can be easily obtained according to the theoretical formula in this paper.

6 CONCLUSIONS

An efficient design procedure for fiberglass preform is presented in this paper. Only original fiber and matrix properties are required for input. The designed fiber fabric's properties agree pretty well with the measured data.

The experimental data was obtained by inversion. Therefore, it is only necessary to provide a set of test data of the unidirectional composite material, and it is possible to design any multi-axial fiber laying angle and gram weight, and the test performance of the prepared FRP laminate is in good agreement with the predicted value, which can greatly save the current The cost of the structural parameters of the fiber cloth was determined by experimental proofing. Although this paper is based on glass fiber cloth design, the theoretical method and calculation formula are also applicable to the structural parameter design of carbon fiber laminate.

Based on Bridging Model and classical laminate theory, an analytical method for designing structural parameters of fiberglass fabric is introduced in this paper, which only needs to provide elastic modulus and strength of fiber and matrix. If it is not clear whether the interface between fiber and matrix is perfect bonded until failure, it is necessary to provide a transverse tensile strength of unidirectional composites. If the properties of fiber and matrix cannot be accurately determined, the experimental data of unidirectional composites can be retrieved. Therefore, at most a set of unidirectional composite testing data can be provided to design arbitrary multi-axial fiber laying angle and weight. The test performance of FRP laminates prepared accords well with the predicted value, which can greatly save the cost of determining the structural parameters of fiber cloth through experimental proofing. Although this paper is based on fiberglass fabric, the theoretical method and calculation formula are also applicable to the structural parameter design of carbon fiber laminates.

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Appendix A. Expression of $[A_{ij}]$ and $[B_{ij}]$

Non-zero matrix element of A_{ij} and B_{ij} are given by [5]

$$A_{11} = E^m / E_{11}^f, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$A_{12} = \frac{E_{11}^f \nu_{12}^m - E^m \nu_{12}^f}{E_{11}^f - E^m} (A_{22} - A_{11}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$A_{22} = 0.3 + 0.7 E^m / E_{22}^f \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$A_{33} = 0.3 + 0.7 G^m / G_{12}^f \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$B_{11} = 1 / (V_f + V_m A_{11}) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$B_{12} = -(V_m A_{12}) / [(V_f + V_m A_{11})(V_f + V_m A_{22})] \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$B_{22} = 1 / (V_f + V_m A_{22}) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$B_{33} = 1 / (V_f + V_m A_{33}) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where E_{11}^f , E_{22}^f , G_{12}^f and ν_{12}^f are the axial modulus, transverse modulus, in-plane shear modulus and axial Poisson's ratio of fibers, E^m , G^m and ν^m are the elastic modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of matrix, respectively.

Appendix B. SCF of perfect interface

$$K_{22}^t = \left[1 + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} A + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} (3 - V_f - \sqrt{V_f}) B \right] \frac{(V_f + 0.3V_m)E_{22}^f + 0.7V_m E^m}{0.3E_{22}^f + 0.7E^m} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$K_{22}^c = \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} A \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} + \frac{B}{2(1 - \sqrt{V_f})} \left[-V_f^2 \left(1 - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{(\sigma_{u,c}^m + \sigma_{u,t}^m)V_f}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right) - \sqrt{V_f} \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} + 1 - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right)^2 \right) \right] \right\} \times \frac{(V_f + 0.3V_m)E_{22}^f + 0.7V_m E^m}{0.3E_{22}^f + 0.7E^m} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$K_{12} = \left[1 - V_f \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m} \{W(V_f) - \frac{1}{3}\} \right] \frac{(V_f + A_{33}V_m)}{A_{33}} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$W(V_f) = \pi \sqrt{V_f} \left[\frac{1}{4V_f} - \frac{4}{128} - \frac{2}{512} V_f - \frac{5}{4096} V_f^2 \right] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $\sigma_{u,t}^m$ and $\sigma_{u,c}^m$ are tensile and compressive strength of matrix.

Appendix C. Transverse tensile SCF after fiber and matrix interface crack

$$\hat{K}_{22}^t = \hat{K}_{22}^t(\psi) = \text{Re} \left\{ e^{-2i\psi} M (be^{i\psi})(a^2/b - b) - e^{-i\psi} \left(N_2 - N_1 \left(\frac{a^2}{b} e^{-i\psi} \right) \right) \right. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

$$\left. + e^{-i\psi} (2 + e^{-2i\psi}) [N(be^{i\psi}) - N_3] \right\} \frac{(V_f + 0.3V_m)E_{22}^f + 0.7V_mE^m}{2(b-a)(0.3E_{22}^f + 0.7E^m)}$$

$$N(z) = Fz + \frac{a^2k}{z} - (z - ae^{i\psi})^{0.5+i\lambda} (z - ae^{-i\psi})^{0.5-i\lambda} \left[(F - 0.5) - \frac{D}{a^2z} \right] \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$N_1(z) = Fz + \frac{a^2k}{z} + \frac{1}{\xi} (z - ae^{i\psi})^{0.5+i\lambda} (z - ae^{-i\psi})^{0.5-i\lambda} \left[(F - 0.5) - \frac{D}{a^2z} \right] \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$N_2 = aFe^{-i\psi} + ake^{i\psi}, \quad N_3 = Fae^{i\psi} + e^{-i\psi}ak, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$M(z) = F - \frac{a^2k}{z^2} - [(F - 0.5)z + H + \frac{C}{z} + \frac{D}{z^2}] \chi(z) \quad (\text{C.5})$$

$$F = \frac{1 - (\cos\psi + 2\lambda \sin\psi) \exp[2\lambda(\pi - \psi)] + (1-k)(1 + 4\lambda^2) \sin^2\psi}{\frac{4}{k} - 2 - 2(\cos\psi + 2\lambda \sin\psi) \exp[2\lambda(\pi - \psi)]} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

$$H = a(\cos\psi + 2\lambda \sin\psi)(0.5 - F) \quad (\text{C.7})$$

$$C = (k - 1)(\cos\psi - 2\lambda \sin\psi)a^2 \exp[2\lambda(\psi - \pi)] \quad (\text{C.8})$$

$$D = (1 - k)a^3 \exp[2\lambda(\psi - \pi)] \quad (\text{C.9})$$

$$\chi(z) = (z - ae^{i\psi})^{-0.5+i\lambda} (z - ae^{-i\psi})^{-0.5-i\lambda} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

$$k = \frac{G^m(1 + \kappa_2)}{(1 + \xi)(G^m + \kappa_1 G_{23}^f)}, \quad \lambda = -(\ln\xi)/(2\pi), \quad \xi = (G_{23}^f + \kappa_2 G^m)/(G^m + \kappa_1 G_{23}^f) \quad (\text{C.11})$$

$$\kappa_1 = 3 - 4\nu^m, \quad \kappa_2 = \frac{3 - \nu_{23}^f - 4\nu_{12}^f \nu_{21}^f}{1 + \nu_{23}^f}, \quad b = a/\sqrt{V_f} \quad (\text{C.12})$$

In the above, ψ is a root solution to the following equation:

$$\text{Re} \left\{ \left(G_0 - \frac{1}{k} - \frac{2(1-k)}{k \exp(i\varphi)} \exp[2\lambda(\psi - \pi)] \right) R(e^{i\varphi}) \right\}_{\varphi=\psi-\gamma} = 0 \quad (\text{C.13})$$

$$R(\exp(i\varphi)) = [\exp(i\varphi) - e^{i\psi}]^{0.5+i\lambda} [\exp(i\varphi) - e^{-i\psi}]^{0.5-i\lambda} \exp(-i\varphi) \quad (\text{C.14})$$

$$G_0 = \frac{1 - (\cos\psi + 2\lambda \sin\psi) \exp[2\lambda(\pi - \psi)] + (1-k)(1 + 4\lambda^2) \sin^2\psi}{2 - k - k(\cos\psi + 2\lambda \sin\psi) \exp[2\lambda(\pi - \psi)]} \quad (\text{C.15})$$

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} \frac{2\lambda(J_1^2 + J_2^2)}{J_1^2 + J_2^2 - 2J_2J_3}, & \text{if } \xi < 1 \\ -\frac{2\lambda(J_1^2 + J_2^2)}{J_1^2 + J_2^2 - 2J_2J_3}, & \text{if } \xi > 1 \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.16})$$

$$J_1 = kG_0 - 1 - 2(1-k)\xi \exp(2\lambda\psi) \cos(\psi) \quad (\text{C.17})$$

$$J_2 = 2(1-k)\xi \exp(2\lambda\psi) \sin(\psi) \quad (\text{C.18})$$

$$J_3 = 2(1-k)\xi \exp(2\lambda\psi) [J_1 \cos(\psi) - J_2 \sin(\psi)] / J_2 \quad (\text{C.19})$$

It is noted that $\xi=1$ corresponds to a singular crack and no solution for can be found. However, one can always adjust a fiber or matrix property such that $\xi \neq 1$ owing to the fact that any measurement for the property involves a deviation.